

Urban biowaste valorization: what's the menu? The H2020 HOOP project's state-of-the-art

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The HOOP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101000836

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CCRI Project

Who we are?

CETENMA

Centro Tecnológico
de la Energía y del
Medio Ambiente

The **Technology Centre for Energy and the Environment, CETENMA** (Cartagena, Spain), is a private, non-profit Business Association, which was set up to support companies with technological research, development and innovation in all areas related to Energy and the Environment, thereby assisting them in becoming more competitive.

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DRAXIS
ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGIES

1. The issue with urban biowaste

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An initiative
of the

The issue with urban biowaste

Organic fraction municipal waste (OFMSW)

selectively collected.

Households, HoReCa, Waste from street markets

Green waste from parks and gardens

Urban waste water sludge (UWWS)

Specific municipal biowaste separately collected

Rejections / fractions from composting and anaerobic digestion

Compulsory separate collection since 01/01/2024!

Status of biowaste management

COMPOSTING

Image Freepik

They are both
very good but...
ONLY 2?

Where is the
menu?

THE SAME SOLUTION DOES
NOT WORK EVERYWHERE
NEED TO GET HIGHER
ADDED-VALUE

THEY ALSO HAVE
DRAWBACKS

ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

Image Freepik

2. The answer: urban circular bioeconomy

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Urban circular bioeconomy concept

Publications Patents Research projects Start-ups

Many opportunities, but how to find your way?

HOOP Methodology to make the menu of technologies

This is the menu: Portfolio of 17 technologies for urban biowaste and wastewater sludge

D2.2 State-of-the-art of technologies for the production of bioproducts from biowaste and wastewater

Author(s): CETENMA, CETAQUA, Draxis, ITENE, Nafigate, RdA, SAV, SfC

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Feedstock	Technology	Bioproducts
AD biogas	Bioprocess anaerob	g from the High-protein feed and food supplements
OFMSW, AD digestate	Black Soldier	duction Feed, frass, proteins, lipids, chitin
AD dewatering liquid	Nutrients re	digestion Phosphorus and nitrogane-based biofertilizers
Meat/fish by-products	Biochemical	s Collagen hydrolysate and active petides
OFMSW, UWWS	Production rhizobac	-promoting Biofertilizers, biostimulants
OFMSW, garden waste, cellulosic rejections	Ethyl Lactat	Biosolvent, chemical building blocks
OFMSW (fruits/vegetables)	Polylactic A	Biopolymer
Used cooking oils	Fermentatio	Bioplastic, cosmetics
Spent coffee grounds	Fermentatio	Nutraceutical products and food additives
UWWS	Biochar from	Biochar (biofertilizer)
UWWS	Bioconversi	Bioplastic
UWWS	Volatile fatty	ge Chemical building blocks
OFMSW, UWWS, garden waste	Bioprocess	n waste Chemical additive
AD biogas	Bioconversi	tems Chemical building blocks
OFMSW	Microalgae	High-protein and omega-3-rich feed
OFMSW, horeca waste	Bioconversi	Biopolymers
OFMSW	Production of biopesticides Bacillus thuringiensis from OFMSW	Biopesticide

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Bioproducts by market sector

Chemistry

Volatile fatty acids
Acetate
Ethanol
Biosolvent (ethyl lactate)
2,3-Butanediol

Biopolymers

PHAs
PLA

Cosmetics

Bioplastics
Bioactive
Ingredients

Nutrition

Single Cell Protein
Insects (protein, fat, chitin)
Animal feed
Nutraceuticals (carotenoids,
active peptides)

Agriculture

Biofertilizers (PGPR)
Biopesticides (Bt)
Phosphorus/nitrogen fertilizers
(struvite, ammonium sulphate)
Biochar
Insect frass

And more coming soon...

Results

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VISUAL SUMMARY OF PROCESSES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF BIOPRODUCTS FROM BIOWASTE AND WASTEWATER

LEGEND

- OFMSW valorization path
- UWWS valorization path
- ⋯→ Valorization of specific biowaste
- 1st line treatment
- Next treatments
- Bioproduct
- Material output
- ⚡ to energy production

Circular Economy is, first of all, ECONOMY

Building the new economic paradigm is like building a house

Materials

Biowaste valorization technologies

Tools

Economic ecosystem for the bioproduct(s)

House

Successful Circular Bioeconomy Business

Results

1. Waste management solutions are **multistep industrial processes**

1. Flexibility

1. Different processes can provide **the same function** (i.e. hydrolysis)
2. A same technology might be applied to different biowaste

1. Biowaste **quality** is usually critical!

1. **BE AWARE OF REGULATORY!**

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Results

- Replacement of existing linear products
- Economic value of the bioproducts and TRL are key factors for feasibility
- Higher added-value by downstreaming
- Social aspects: odours, noise, price

- Robustness in insect farming or pyrolysis
- Specific biowaste technologies:
 - Good for agrofood by-products
 - Regulatory advantages

To Learn more
contact me

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What is HOOP?

 23 partners
10 countries

€9M

Budget

€5.8M PDA management

€8M EC Contribution

€51.7M

Investment
Induced

Oct
2020

Jun
2023

Oct
2024

How to unlock investments in urban circular bioeconomy?

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Learn more: HOOP Urban Circular Bioeconomy Hub

Virtual Academy

HOOP Bio-Circularity Label

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HOOP Network of Cities and Regions

**Thank you very much for
your attention!**

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